

Special Relativity Linked to Generalized Index of Refraction i.e. $1/v(\text{relative})$ For a Moving Mirror?

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Fermat's principle (in general) is linked to a stationary path for: $\int n ds$ where n is the index of refraction and ds is a three space interval. In (1) it is argued that for special relativity ds becomes dT where T is proper time $t \sqrt{1-vv}$ and $L = m \sqrt{1-vv} - V(x)$ with $c=1$. For a free particle then $\int m \sqrt{1-vv} dT$ should be stationary and rest mass m is linked to n .

In (2) we argued that for a mirror moving in the negative y direction with constant v one could map n , the index of refraction to $1/v(\text{relative})$ for both the incident and reflected rays. In (3) we argued that $v(\text{relative}) = \int dt'(\text{moving frame}) / \int dt(\text{lab frame})$ ((1)). This was shown explicitly using Lorentz transformations, but here we argue that one does not need to know the explicit form of the Lorentz transformation to link the moving mirror to special relativity. Ultimately we find that a generalized index of refraction is linked to ((1)) with ds remaining as a spatial distance and not becoming dT with m taking the place of the index of refraction for the moving mirror problem. In this approach, however, we are no longer varying x as in Fermat's principle. Instead we use the hypothetical velocity approach which is equivalent to having the x velocity projection in the moving frame remain constant for the moving and reflected rays i.e. incident angle equals reflected in the moving frame with c the same in the moving and lab frame.

Proper Time as Spatial Interval from (1)

Fermat's principle of least time may be formulated in terms of: $\int n ds$ being stationary where n is the index of refraction. Often $n(y)$ because a mirror or medium interface is taken to be along the x axis. We follow this convention.

In (1) proper time $T = t(\text{lab}) \sqrt{1-vv}$ ($c=1$) and ds (special rel) $ds = dx dx + dy dy - dt dt$ ($c=1$). It may then be shown that $dT = ds$ (special rel). This is then used with the special relativistic Lagrangian:

$$\int dT (m \sqrt{1-vv} - V(x)) \quad \text{where } V(x) \text{ is a potential and } m \text{ rest mass. } ((2))$$

For no potential m is compared with the index of refraction in Fermat's principle and integration is over proper time.

Here we wish to show that for a moving mirror problem, one may still use the regular ds (non relativistic) and that a generalized n , linked to relative velocity, is linked to a ratio of the time interval in the moving frame divided by that in the lab frame separately for the incident ray and the reflected. We follow the ideas we presented in (2) and (3).

Moving Mirror Problem

Fermat's principle of least time may be formulated for a mirror of length L in the x direction moving in the downward y direction with constant speed v with the incident ray hitting at x and the reflected ray traveling such that it covers $L-x$ on the x axis. Specifically one calculates t_a+t_b in terms of x and then takes $d/dx (t_a+t_b)=0$ (see (4)) to find:

$\sin(A) - \sin(B) = -v/c \sin(A+B)$ where A and B are the incident and reflected angles with respect to the y axis ((2))

In (3) we argued that this may be expressed in terms of relative velocities (along the incident and reflected ray directions) i.e.

$$\sin(A) / v(\text{relative A}) = \sin(B) / v(\text{relative B}) \quad ((3))$$

In particular $v(\text{relative A}) = 1-v \cos(A)$ and $v(\text{relative B}) = v \cos(B) + 1$ for $c=1$ ((4))

Let t_a and t_b be the times that the incident and reflected rays travel with the y axis projection being the same. Then $\sin A = x/ct_a$ and $\sin B = (x-L)/ct_b$ (set $c=1$).

So far no mention of special relativity or alternative frames has been made. Given that the mirror travels with a speed v in the negative y direction, one, however, may naturally introduce a frame also moving in the negative y direction with speed v . Assuming as special relativistic theory does that x and $L-x$ lengths do not change because they are perpendicular to the frame motion. Then:

$$x / t_a(\text{moving frame}) = (L-x) / t_b(\text{moving frame}) \quad ((5))$$

The speed of light remains c as seen in the moving frame following Einstein's assumption. Multiplying ((5)) by $1/c$ shows that in the moving frame:

$$x/\text{hypotenuse}(a) = \cos(A') = (L-x)/\text{hypotenuse}(b) = \cos(B') \quad ((6))$$

Or $A'=B'$ in the moving frame which is the usual angle of incidence equals angle of reflection for a stationary mirror. In the moving frame the mirror is stationary.

Now $\sin(A) = x / t_a$ and $\sin(B) = (L-x)/t_b$ where t_a and t_b are time intervals in the lab frame. Thus ((6)) means that:

$$\sin(A) / \{t_a(\text{moving})/t_a(\text{lab})\} = \sin(B) / \{t_b(\text{moving})/t_b(\text{lab})\} \quad ((7))$$

Comparing ((6)) and ((7)) shows that:

$$v(\text{relative } i) = \{t_i(\text{moving})/t_i(\text{lab})\} \quad \text{where } i=a,b \quad ((8))$$

Thus there is a direct link between relative velocities in the lab frame and time intervals in both the moving and lab frames. The time intervals in the moving frame may be explicitly calculated using Lorentz transformations as done in (2) to show that ((8)) does in fact hold.

In (3) we noted that n in Fermat's principle is linked to c/n i.e. the speed of light in a medium. We generalized this idea to suggest that for the moving mirror problem:

$n \rightarrow 1/v(\text{relative})$ ((9)) so linking with special relativity suggests:

$n \rightarrow 1/v(\text{relative}) \rightarrow \text{time interval (lab)} / \text{time interval (moving frame)}$ ((10))

Thus the effects of special relativity may be incorporated into the generalized index of refraction and one may think of motion in 3 space. Time intervals in the moving and lab frames due, however, come into the picture as shown in ((10)). Motion, however, is still in straight lines (geodesics) in space even in different frames of special relativity.

Thus we think that one may still use ds as a 3-space related quantity i.e. Fermat's principle may be used in different frames.

This begs the question of how one may solve the moving mirror problem. Equating momentum projections along the x axis leads to $p(\text{incident}) \sin(A) = p(\text{reflected}) \sin(B)$ which has too many unknowns. One may use Fermat's principle in the lab frame leading to ((2)). One may use a hypothetical velocity H approach such that $H \sin(A) = v(\text{relative } a)$ and $H \sin(B) = v(\text{relative } b)$ which does not require taking d/dx derivatives and setting them equal to 0. Alternatively one may solve the stationary mirror problem in the moving frame by first Lorentz transforming lab quantities to the moving frame and then transforming the results back to the lab. All three approaches yield the same results.

It is interesting to note that if the usual Fermat's principle is applied to the moving mirror problem, one already uses a straight line ray for the incident and reflected rays which means one is already using part of the solution in the problem. Then one minimizes time (through changing x). In the approach suggested above using relative velocities one no longer minimizes, but rather thinks in terms of a conserved horizontal velocity. In the lab frame this H (hypothetical velocity) does not seem physical, but in the moving frame it becomes $1/H$ which is the x projection of the velocity of light which is the same for the incident and reflected rays because there is no mirror motion.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that although there may be approaches (1) which map ds (3 space) to ds (special relativistic) = d proper time, for the moving problem one may still use ds (3 space) and generalize n , the index of refraction in optical Lagrangian theory to $1/v(\text{relative})$ for the incident and reflected rays (like two indexes of refraction). These in turn we argue are linked to $t(\text{lab}) / t(\text{moving frame})$ for the incident and reflected rays. Thus special relativistic quantities are

incorporated within n . In such an approach, one no longer performs a variation (of x as in Fermat's minimum time principle for which $t(\text{incident}) + t(\text{reflected})$ is a function of x). Rather one uses the hypothetical velocity approach $H \sin(A) = v(\text{relative } a)$ and $H \sin(B) = v(\text{relative } b)$. In this note we show that in a moving frame x and $L-x$ remain the same (as they are perpendicular to motion). The $x/t_a(\text{moving}) = (L-x) / t_b(\text{moving})$ with c the same as in the lab implies that $\cos(A') = \cos(B')$ which is a stationary mirror solution as the mirror is stationary in the moving frame. This, however, may be interpreted as $1/H = 1/H$ i.e a constant velocity along the x axis in the moving frame. This also shows that $v(\text{relative})$ is equivalent to $t_a(\text{moving}) / t_a(\text{lab})$.

References

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